

Macroeconomic Stability and Its Determinants in Emerging Markets

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Abstract

The impact of external shocks on macroeconomic fluctuations holds significant practical importance for enhancing the economic resilience of developing countries and promoting financial openness. This paper employs a Panel Conditional Homogeneous Vector Autoregression model with exogenous variables (PCHVAR-X) to investigate the internal and external determinants of macroeconomic fluctuations in emerging market economies at different stages of financial openness. The results show that global demand shocks are the most dominant external factor, accounting for approximately 30% of global output variation in both the short and long term. Among domestic factors, financial market pressure is the most significant driver of volatility. In the short term, domestic shocks contribute over 80% to macroeconomic fluctuations, but the influence of external shocks intensifies over time, such as rising from 8.41% at a financial openness level of 50% in the short term to 34.85% in the long term. The response to global monetary policy tightening exhibits an inverted "V"-shaped pattern, with initial mitigation followed by intensified volatility due to liquidity constraints. Additionally, variance decomposition indicates that commodity supply shocks contribute up to 45% to long-term commodity price volatility. The findings underscore that financial openness amplifies the effects of global shocks while also modifying the transmission mechanisms of domestic risks. These insights provide valuable guidance for emerging economies to design differentiated policy strategies balancing openness, resilience, and macroeconomic stability.

Keywords: *Macroeconomic, emerging markets, external/internal shocks, PCHVAR-X model, economic volatility.*

JEL Classification codes: *E44, F62, O11.*

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Introduction

With the collective rise of emerging economies over recent decades, these nations have not only demonstrated rapid economic expansion but have also made significant strides in enhancing their institutional frameworks. Improvements in governance quality, regulatory environments, and macroeconomic management have strengthened the foundations of their financial and economic systems. At the same time, the continuous optimization of industrial structures, such as through a shift from traditional resource-based sectors to high-value-added manufacturing and services, has been complemented by the rapid growth of the digital economy (Wang & Zhu, 2025; Sturgeon, 2021; Rani et al., 2024). Emerging markets are increasingly embracing digital transformation, leveraging innovations in e-commerce, fintech, and digital infrastructure to enhance productivity and inclusiveness (Syahid et al., 2025). The rise of digital finance, including mobile payments, digital banking, and blockchain-based services, has expanded access to financial services and improved capital allocation, especially in underbanked populations (Mhlanga, 2023). As a result, emerging markets have transitioned from peripheral actors to central contributors, now serving as a critical engine propelling global economic growth, particularly in the context of stagnation or slower recovery in many advanced economies.

The protracted nature of geopolitical risks such as Sino-US trade frictions and the Russia-Ukraine conflict, coupled with high global inflationary pressures and supply chain challenges like raw material shortages and shipping delays, have plunged the world economy into a state of high uncertainty. Financial openness strengthens the linkages between domestic and international markets through global financial channels. While it facilitates the optimal allocation of global financial resources, it also transmits external shocks to the domestic financial system. Existing research indicates that external shocks are a significant source of macroeconomic fluctuations in a country (Maćkowiak, 2007). In the context of financial openness,

- What role do external shocks play in macroeconomic fluctuations?
- Given the complex interplay of internal and external shocks, are macroeconomic fluctuations primarily driven by external shocks or internal factors?
- Different countries exhibit distinct stages of financial openness. Does an increase in the degree of financial openness mitigate or amplify macroeconomic volatility?
- Furthermore, what are the differences in the mechanisms through which internal and external shocks exert their influence during this process?

To investigate these questions, this paper employs a Panel Conditional Homogeneous Vector Autoregression model with exogenous variables (PCHVAR-X) to examine the impact of domestic and foreign shocks on macroeconomic fluctuations in emerging economies and the role of financial openness in this mechanism. The marginal contributions of this paper are as:

- Proposes a PCHVAR-X model to jointly analyze how internal and external shocks affect macroeconomic fluctuations.
- Applies sign restrictions via SVAR to compare internal vs. external shocks across openness levels and guide financial policies.

Literature Review

A substantial body of research has delved deeply into the sources of macroeconomic fluctuations (Barrot et al., 2018). Financial openness, as a key measure of financial liberalization reforms, and its relationship with the macroeconomy have garnered widespread academic attention. Financial

openness primarily affects the macroeconomy through channels such as capital flows (Forbes & Warnock, 2021), exchange rates (Carnevali et al., 2024), credit (Kumar & Prasanna, 2024), and asset prices (Diaz & Collin, 2025). Some scholars argue that financial openness facilitates asset portfolio diversification and disperses financial risk through mechanisms that interconnect markets across borders (Liu, 2025). Furthermore, by lowering barriers to entry and exit for domestic and foreign financial institutions, it promotes cross-border credit activities and enhances resource allocation efficiency (Larrain & Stumpner, 2017). However, other scholars point out that financial openness may trigger instability in cross-border capital flows. Large-scale inflows of speculative capital can lead to asset bubble accumulation, reduced resource allocation efficiency, and a decline in export competitiveness. In the short term, panic-driven capital flight can also induce currency liquidity risks (Mammadov, 2025). Additionally, the "crowding-out" effect from an influx of foreign financial institutions can easily increase the risk appetite of domestic financial institutions. Financial openness also strengthens the interconnectedness of global financial markets, leading to increased asset price volatility, which exacerbates financial system risks and impacts macroeconomic stability.

The mechanism through which financial openness affects the macroeconomy is relatively complex. Sordi et al., (2006) noted that the economic effects of financial openness depend on a country's internal and external economic and financial factors, including its industrial structure, economic policies, and the level of financial development. Numerous studies have explored the specific impacts of a country's internal factors (Stanley et al., 2001; Bostan et al., 2023). However, as the degree of financial openness increases and external dependency strengthens, the role of external shocks becomes increasingly significant.

Currently, academic views on the impact of external shocks are divided. In contrast, Klingelhöfer et al. (2019) find that foreign demand shocks have the most persistent impact on China's economic fluctuations. Moreover, the impact of shocks varies by country and economic cycle. Since financial openness enhances the linkage between domestic and international markets, existing research has made useful explorations into whether financial openness affects the role of external shocks. Almansour et al., (2015), using a SVAR model to study the impact of external shocks on emerging economies, found that financial openness amplifies the negative impact of external borrowing shocks on economic growth. Chaitip et al., (2014) employed a PCHVAR-X model in their research, found that financial openness amplifies the impact of external shocks on economic volatility in the short term, but helps reduce volatility in the long run. Zheng et al., (2024) constructed a multi-sector DSGE model for a small open economy, found that financial openness amplifies the negative impact of external shocks on the domestic economy.

Existing research shows inconsistent views on the relative importance of external shocks. Furthermore, literature that incorporates financial openness, external shocks, and macroeconomic fluctuations within a unified research framework remains relatively limited. Most studies focus on exploring linear transmission mechanisms or theoretical rationales. In reality, financial openness is a complex process in which a country gradually relaxes financial controls to achieve free cross-border capital movement. Significant differences exist among countries in terms of economic structure and institutions. Therefore, considering the time-varying effects of financial openness and the heterogeneous characteristics of national economic fluctuations is particularly important.

Empirical Research Design

Model Selection

To investigate the impact of internal and external factor shocks on economic fluctuations across countries, clarify the role of varying degrees of financial openness within this mechanism, and characterize asymmetric and time-varying features, this paper introduces exogenous variables to

comprehensively account for both internal and external influences, establishing a PCHVAR-X model. This model relaxes the restriction of constant slope coefficients, allowing coefficients to depend on time-varying country-specific characteristics. It thereby improves upon standard PVAR models, which are unable to measure the heterogeneity and time-varying structural features of policy effects across economies, while also overcoming the limitation of Time-Varying Parameter Vector Autoregression with Stochastic Volatility (TVP-VAR-SV) models based on Bayesian MCMC estimation methods, which are typically confined to estimating time series for a single economy (Boukhatem & Djelassi, 2022; Zhang et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2022). The model is specified as:

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + A_1(z_{i,t})Y_{i,t-1} + A_2(z_{i,t})Y_{i,t-2} + \dots + A_p(z_{i,t})Y_{i,t-p} + B_0(z_{i,t})X_t + \dots + B_q(z_{i,t})X_{t-q} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

where, $Y_{i,t}$ and X_t , respectively, represent a domestic variable and an exogenous global variable. According to the analysis in the previous text, financial openness will affect economic and financial factors. Therefore, the endogenous variables selected in the article are the economic growth and financial risk situation of each country. p, q represents the lag order. α_i represents deterministic terms such as fixed effects, time trend terms, and seasonal dummy variables. $z_{i,t}$ is a conditional variable that represents the degree of financial openness of different countries i at different times t . Due to the relatively small impact of emerging market countries on the global economy, this article refers to Maćkowiak et al., (2007), and others to construct a model using the following method:

$$\sum_{s=0}^p \begin{bmatrix} A_{11}(s) & A_{12}(s) \\ A_{21}(s) & A_{22}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Y_{i,t-s}^d \\ X_{t-s}^e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_t^d \\ \varepsilon_t^e \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where, similar to equation (1), the variable $Y_{i,t}^d$ is a vector reflecting the economic situation of country i , and X_t^e is a vector of global economic variables. ε_t^d and ε_t^e are the internal and external structural impact vectors, respectively. $\varepsilon_t[\varepsilon_t^d, \varepsilon_t^e]'$ is a Gaussian random vector that satisfies $E[\varepsilon_t | y_{t-s}, s > 0] = 0$ and $E[\varepsilon_t \varepsilon_t' | y_{t-s}, s > 0] = I$. Assuming that the domestic impact ε_t^d does not affect the external variable ε_t^e .

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j Y_{i,t-j} + \sum_{h=0}^q b_h' X_{t-h} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

here, $i = 1, \dots, N$; $t = 1, \dots, T$. j and h , respectively, represent the lag order. Furthermore, this study introduces $z_{i,t}$ as a conditional variable. Assuming that each scalar coefficient $a_{j,sm}(z_{i,t})$ in $A_j(\cdot)$ can be approximated by a polynomial of the conditional variable $z_{i,t}$, i.e

$$a_{j,sm}(z_{i,t}) \sim \pi(z_{i,t}) \times \gamma_{j,sm} \quad (4)$$

where, $\pi(z_{i,t}) = [\pi_1(z_{i,t}), \pi_2(z_{i,t}), \dots, \pi_\tau(z_{i,t})]$, for the polynomial system of $z_{i,t}$, $\gamma_{j,sm} = (\gamma_{j,sm1}, \gamma_{j,sm2}, \dots, \gamma_{j,sm\tau})'$ is the polynomial coefficient, and the coefficient matrix $A_j(\cdot)$ can be written as:

$$A_i(z_{i,t}) = \begin{bmatrix} \pi(z_{i,t}) \cdot \gamma_{j,11} & \cdots & \pi(z_{i,t}) \cdot \gamma_{j,1K} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \pi(z_{i,t}) \cdot \gamma_{j,K1} & \cdots & \pi(z_{i,t}) \times \gamma_{j,KK} \\ & & \pi'(z_{i,t}) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma'_{j,11} & \gamma'_{j,12} & \cdots & \gamma'_{j,1K} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \gamma'_{j,K1} & \gamma'_{j,K2} & \cdots & \gamma'_{j,KK} \end{bmatrix} \times [I_K \otimes \pi'(z_{i,t})] \quad (5)$$

$$A_i(z_{i,t}) = \Gamma_j \cdot [I_K \otimes \pi'(z_{i,t})] \quad (6)$$

By processing the coefficient matrix $B_h(\cdot)$, the PCHVARX model can be organized as follows:

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \sum_{j=1}^p \gamma'_j(z_{i,t} Y_{i,t-j}) + \sum_{h=0}^q \lambda'_h (I_M \otimes z_{i,t}) X_{t-h} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

Identification of Exogenous Shocks

Referring to Peersman et al., (2025), and others, this study considers the impact of global demand, global supply, global monetary policy, and international commodity shocks, and constructs a structural vector autoregression (SVAR) model, as:

$$X_t = \beta + \sum_{j=1}^r C_j X_{t-j} + v_t \quad (8)$$

where, X_t is a global variable, including global output growth y_t^w , global interest rates i_t^w , global inflation π_t^w , and global commodity prices oil_t^w . Global structural shocks $\varepsilon_t = [\varepsilon_t^d \varepsilon_t^s \varepsilon_t^m \varepsilon_t^e]$, including global demand, supply, monetary policy, and commodity shocks. This study uses the symbolic constraint method to identify SVAR models. According to Barrot et al., (2018), based on the IS-LM and AD-AS models, the symbol constraint settings in this study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Identification Symbol Constraints

	Global output	Global inflation	Short term interest rate	Bulk prices
Global demand shock	-	-	-	-
Global supply shock	-	+	?	-
Global monetary policy shock	-	-	+	-
Global commodity shock	-	+	?	+

In Table 1, the weak global demand shock will lower global output levels, inflation levels, short-term interest rates, and commodity prices. Negative global commodity supply shocks will reduce global output growth, increase inflation levels, and lower relative prices of goods. Tight global

monetary policy will lead to an increase in short-term interest rates. And it has a negative impact on output, inflation, and commodity prices. The reduction in commodity supply leads to an increase in commodity prices, which has a negative impact on output and a positive impact on inflation.

Financial openness can affect the financial market through multiple channels such as bank credit, stock prices, and foreign exchange fluctuations. This study refers to select indicators from the three financial sub markets of banks, stocks, and foreign exchange to construct the Financial Stress Index (FSI) ①, which measures the risk of the financial system. Existing literature mostly constructs financial stress index based on the data of banks, stocks, foreign exchange and bond markets. However, due to the lack of stress data of bond markets and the leading role of banks and foreign exchange markets in financial risk contagion in emerging markets (Cardareli et al., 2019), and the short-term interest rate of U.S. treasury bond bonds can reflect the pressure of short-term international bond markets, this paper selects banks, stocks and foreign exchange markets to calculate financial stress index, taking into account the comprehensiveness and representativeness of the sample. This article shortens the sample period to construct a financial stress index containing bond market data, and the results are robust. Due to space limitations, the relevant results have not been listed. Interested readers can request them from the author.

After standardizing the sub indicators, the average is taken to construct the quarterly FSI. This article uses event testing to examine the effectiveness of the financial stress index. Taking China as an example, it was found that early 2001, 2008, and 2015 were periods of financial pressure. The higher the value, the greater the risk. The selection and calculation of other exogenous and conditional variables are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Variable Construction

	Variable	Variable symbol	Variable description
Endogenous variable	Macroeconomics	vol(gdp)	Standard deviation of logarithmic year-on-year growth rate of actual GDP.
	financial market	FSI	Financial Market Index
Global variables	Global output	y	Global real GDP growth rate
	Global inflation	π	US GDP deflator index
	Short term interest rate	I	3-month T-bill interest rate in the US
	Commodity prices	oil	CRB Index/US GDP deflator
Condition variable	Financial openness	open	(Total external assets + total liabilities)/GDP

Drawing on the work of Li et al., 2024, taking into account data availability and sample validity, this study selects 26 emerging economies as the research subjects. These include: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, and Peru from Latin America; China, India, Indonesia, Israel, South Korea, Malaysia, Pakistan, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Turkey from Asia; the Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania, and Russia from Europe; and Egypt, Morocco, and South Africa from Africa. The sample period spans from 2000 to 2020 at a quarterly frequency. Relevant data are sourced from the IFS, Bloomberg, Data-stream, EIU Country-data, World Bank, and Wind databases.

Empirical Process and Results Analysis

Identification and Interaction of External Shocks

To identify the external factors of macroeconomic fluctuations, this paper employs the sign restrictions specified in Table 1 to examine the relationships among external factors. The impulse response results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Impact of Global External Shocks on Global Variables

First, a negative global demand shock initially induces negative responses in output, inflation, interest rates, and commodity prices. Subsequently, its impact on inflation and commodity prices gradually diminishes. Its effect on output turns positive after the 8th period, while its influence on interest rates remains persistently negative. This indicates that in the short term, reduced demand leads to declines in real output and price levels, triggering an economic recession. This downturn lowers the transaction demand for money and reduces interest rates. However, in the long run, due to "frictions" such as rational expectations, opaque information, and nominal wages, the effects of the demand shock dissipate. Output may gradually increase, partly sustained by prolonged low interest rates.

The effect of a negative global supply shock is similar to that of a demand shock, meaning a short-term supply reduction can push up prices, but the overall outcome still manifests as declines in output, interest rates, and prices.

Furthermore, a global monetary policy tightening shock initially causes a positive response in short-term interest rates, which turns negative after the 5th period. Output, inflation, and commodity prices all show negative responses, with the output response being relatively more persistent. This suggests that monetary tightening reduces liquidity and raises interest rates, increasing corporate financing costs, suppressing output, and fostering expectations of falling prices. The resulting contractions in both production and investment drive down commodity prices.

Finally, a negative commodity supply shock leads to a short-term positive response in commodity prices and inflation, which quickly turns negative and gradually weakens. Global output continues to decline, while interest rates shift from an initial short-term positive response to a negative one. This indicates that a commodity supply shock increases costs of raw materials, pushing up inflation and curbing economic activity, which in turn triggers deflationary expectations and lowers commodity prices. The initial rise in interest rates may stem from inflation expectations, but later, as the global economy slows, lowering interest rates becomes one of the stimulus measures. Tables

3 to 5 presents the variance decomposition results at horizons of 1 quarter, 1 year, and 2 years following global variable shocks.

Table 3. Variance Decomposition Results of Global Variables in (a) Phase 1 (Q1)

	Global demand shock	Global supply shock	Global monetary policy shock	Global commodity shock
Global output	32.26	11.35	22.36	34.03
Global inflation	35.28	31.12	26.42	7.18
Short term interest rate	56.81	11.22	21.71	10.25
Bulk prices	8.80	39.08	10.36	41.75

Table 4. Variance Decomposition Results of Global Variables in (b) Phase 4 (one year)

	Global demand shock	Global supply shock	Global monetary policy shock	Global commodity shock
Global output	33.53	9.66	27.06	29.76
Global inflation	32.23	32.81	26.45	8.49
Short term interest rate	66.44	12.46	10.89	10.21
Bulk prices	9.23	45.44	10.22	35.11

Table 5. Variance Decomposition Results of Global Variables in (c) Phase 8 (two years)

	Global demand shock	Global supply shock	Global monetary policy shock	Global commodity shock
Global output	32.70	9.66	27.98	29.66
Global inflation	32.02	32.56	26.74	8.68
Short term interest rate	67.29	12.61	8.99	11.11
Bulk prices	9.39	45.18	10.40	35.04

First, both global demand shocks and commodity shocks account for approximately 30% of the variation in output in both the short and long term, making them the primary drivers of fluctuations in world real GDP growth. Second, the variance decomposition for global inflation shows that demand, supply, and monetary shocks contribute 32%, 31%, and 26%, respectively, while commodity shocks account for less than 9%. This finding aligns with the results of Barrot et al. (2018) and is consistent with the context of moderate inflation and slowing economic growth. During this period, the sharp decline in oil prices was associated with falling demand and supply-side excesses resulting from the global economic downturn, essentially stemming from changes in supply and demand. Furthermore, changes in interest rates are also primarily driven by global demand shocks.

Regarding commodity price movements, the contribution of global supply shocks is 39% in the short term and 45% in the medium-to-long term, while commodity supply shocks contribute 42% in the short term and 35% in the medium-to-long term. This indicates that commodity prices are more directly influenced by supply factors in the short term, whereas the indirect impact of global supply reductions exerts a stronger effect on commodities in the medium-to-long term.

Impact Mechanism of Internal and External Shocks

This paper employs a PCHVAR-X model with financial openness as a conditioning variable for empirical analysis, to further investigate the internal and external factors influencing economic fluctuations in emerging economies under the context of financial openness.

Impact of External Shocks

The impulse responses of macroeconomic fluctuations to external factor shocks, varying with the degree of financial openness and over time, are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Pulse Response Diagram of Domestic Macroeconomy to External Shocks under Different Levels of Financial Openness

Figure 3. Defending Effect of Financial Openness on Global Monetary Policy Shocks and Impact of Commodity Prices

First, in response to a negative global demand shock, economic fluctuations exhibit a positive response, and the magnitude of this response increases with a higher degree of financial openness. A negative demand shock leads to declines in global output, interest rates, and prices. Weaker demand suppresses import-export trade and investment, intensifying downward pressure on the economy. Countries with higher financial openness have stronger linkages with the global economy and finance, making them more susceptible to negative spillover effects from the world economy. Second, the response to a negative global supply shock is similar, with economic fluctuations showing a positive response that decays to zero relatively quickly. This is because its impact on prices is relatively short-lived, leading to a faster recovery.

Furthermore, when global monetary policy tightens, economic fluctuations and financial pressure exhibit an inverted "V"-shaped pattern. This indicates that monetary tightening, on one hand, triggers asset price declines through liquidity shortages, increasing financial market pressure. On the other hand, it may have a deflationary effect in the short term, temporarily stimulating demand recovery and thereby reducing economic fluctuations to some extent. However, in the long run, liquidity shortages further exacerbate corporate financing constraints, suppressing their investment and production activities, ultimately leading to a renewed increase in economic fluctuations. For

countries with a high degree of financial openness, the high global interest rate environment induced by tightening policies makes capital outflows more likely, further increasing financing difficulties for enterprises, thus amplifying the impact on their economies (Georgiadis, 2014).

Finally, a negative commodity supply shock increases economic volatility. Fluctuations in commodity prices affect output and price levels through trade and price channels, subsequently spreading to relevant sectors of the real economy. The reaction mechanism of financial markets to external shocks is similar to that of the macroeconomy, showing positive responses to global demand and supply shocks, an inverted "V"-shaped response to monetary shocks, and a greater magnitude of impact with higher levels of financial openness.

Impact of Internal Shocks

The impulse responses of domestic macroeconomics and financial markets to shocks, varying across different levels of financial openness and over time, are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Pulse Response Diagram of Internal Shocks under Different Levels of Financial Openness

First, a shock to financial market pressure elicits a positive response that gradually decays. The intensity of this response increases with the degree of financial openness (Figure 4a), indicating that financial openness amplifies the buildup of financial market risks. The financial market's response to macroeconomic shocks is also positive (Figure 4b), suggesting that sharp economic fluctuations, in turn, can trigger financial turmoil, with financial openness reinforcing this feedback effect from the economy to finance.

Second, in response to domestic macroeconomic shocks, the differences among countries with varying openness levels are relatively small (Figure 4d). This is because such shocks primarily circulate within the domestic economy and exhibit less pronounced spillover effects. Financial pressure shocks elicit a positive response in macroeconomic volatility. Financial market stress leads to a downturn in the real economy, with highly open economies showing a smaller response (Figure 4e). This indicates that financial openness mitigates the negative impact of financial market pressure on the macroeconomy.

Finally, this paper also examines the impacts of shocks from different financial sub-markets. The results show that banking market pressure has the greatest effect on economic volatility, and this effect substantially weakens as financial openness increases. The positive response to stock market shocks strengthens with greater openness. In contrast, the foreign exchange market exhibits a short-term negative response. Most emerging economies still rely primarily on indirect financing. Financial openness facilitates the entry of foreign financial institutions, which can improve the management practices of domestic banks and enhance the efficiency of financial services to the real economy through competition and technology spillovers, thereby reducing their risk spillover to the economy (Illing & Liu, 2006; Ma et al., 2022; Levine, 2001). However, financial openness may also intensify risk contagion, affect firms' financing capacity, and exacerbate the stock market's negative impact on the economy. Conversely, currency depreciation can improve export competitiveness, thereby helping to moderate macroeconomic fluctuations.

Variance Decomposition of Internal and External Shocks

Figure 5 presents the variance decomposition results for macroeconomic volatility under internal and external shocks at forecast horizons of 1 quarter, 1 year, and 2 years. For short-term variance contributions to economic volatility, domestic shocks account for over 80%. In the long term, domestic shocks remain the dominant factor. A similar pattern is observed for financial market pressure. Therefore, macroeconomic fluctuations are primarily driven by the feedback between domestic finance and the real economy, consistent with (Levine, 2001; Rodríguez et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the influence of international external shocks on both the macroeconomy and financial markets gradually strengthens over time. At a financial openness level of 50%, the contribution of external shocks to economic fluctuations rises from 8.41% in the short term to 34.85% in the long term. The long-term response of financial markets to external shocks also intensifies. Financial openness amplifies the impact of global shocks because it facilitates economic and trade linkages, making the transmission of external shocks more direct.

Figure 5. Variance Decomposition Results of Macroeconomic Fluctuations on Internal and External Impacts under Different Degrees of Financial Openness

Examining the types of global shocks, short-term economic fluctuations are mainly affected by demand shocks. In the long term, supply shocks also play a role, and the influence of monetary policy shocks gradually increases. The development model of most emerging economies is export-oriented, with high dependence on external demand. Global economic recessions or changes in supply and demand conditions thus affect the stability of their economic and financial markets through trade channels.

Implementation Notes

Based on the research findings, this paper proposes the following policy recommendations:

First, unblocking the domestic economic cycle should be the foremost task for stabilizing the economy, as China's macroeconomic fluctuations are primarily driven by the internal circulation of its economy and finance. It is essential to address all blockages within the national economic circulation. On one hand, continue to improve the domestic demand system by enhancing the supply side's adaptability to domestic demand, while simultaneously raising household income levels to stimulate consumer demand. On the other hand, given the protracted nature of external frictions, strengthen technological innovation and R&D investment to improve the autonomous, controllable capability and long-term competitiveness of domestic industrial and supply chains.

Second, continue to deepen institutional financial openness, proactively building systems from a systemic perspective. Actively participate in international financial governance to establish independent, high-standard rules for openness. Refine the rules for "bringing in" and "going global" in open sectors to balance security and comprehensiveness during the financial opening process. Persistently cultivate a first-class, market-oriented, law-based, and internationalized business environment to reinforce the embeddedness of industrial chains and provide robust support for stabilizing the domestic economic cycle.

Third, effectively prevent and control financial risks. Enhance risk prevention capabilities at the micro-level of financial institutions by conducting regular risk assessments and stress tests. Implement dynamic and comprehensive monitoring of financial market risks, with particular attention to abnormal fluctuations in the banking and stock markets. Continue to improve the macroprudential regulatory framework by introducing intelligent regulatory technologies. Strengthen international regulatory cooperation to jointly participate in the supervision of cross-border financial activities and information sharing, thereby preventing and mitigating the cross-border contagion of financial risks in a timely manner.

Conclusions

The study finds that among external shocks, global demand shocks play a dominant role, determining global supply and interest rate levels. These shocks amplify economic volatility through the feedback mechanism between the real economy and the financial system, with the impact being more pronounced in economies with higher financial openness. In contrast, among internal shocks, financial market pressure exerts a stronger negative effect on the macroeconomy compared to external shocks, and a higher degree of financial openness helps mitigate this negative effect. Financial openness amplifies the negative impact of financial market shocks only during major global events. Overall, shocks from domestic macroeconomic factors and financial pressures remain the primary drivers of macroeconomic fluctuations, although the influence of external shocks gradually increases over time. Furthermore, global financial events lead to a situation where, in the long run, most countries are more affected by external shocks than by domestic ones. When major shocks originate from the real economic sphere, economies with diversified industrial

structures and a greater reliance on domestic circulation demonstrate stronger resilience against external shocks.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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